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UNDERSTANDING ENGINEERING STUDENTS' MATHEMATICS PROFICIENCIES: A STEP TOWARDS SUPPORTING DIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

The economic demand for engineering graduates in South Africa coupled with low throughput in engineering degree programs have highlighted mathematics proficiency as a challenge. As engineering classes become more diverse, uneven mathematics preparation compounds the challenges facing engineering educators. During an engineering module, lecturers and students may come to realise that there is a mismatch between the expected and current mathematical proficiencies needed to engage with the disciplinary content. However, developing the required mathematical proficiencies within disciplines in addition to a full workload may overload students, and lead to failure. Starting with an understanding of the mathematical background of a cohort of students and sharing mathematical proficiency data with engineering lecturers soon after registration can help with planning interventions to develop specific skills needed for students to succeed in particular courses.

This quantitative research profiles the mathematical proficiencies of engineering students at a South African university and poses the questions: Based on pre-university assessments and final grades for a series of three semester-courses in calculus, what mathematical proficiency profiles can be identified? Are the profiles different for other demographic factors? We present an analysis of engineering students at a South African university that includes variables such as gender and grades for three university calculus courses, final school mathematics examinations, and National Benchmark Tests and their mathematics subdomain analysis. We suggest directions for further qualitative research to support the design of suitable interventions for diverse engineering classes.

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1 INTRODUCTION

In South Africa there is a national desire to increase participation in engineering [1]. Most South African higher education engineering programmes accept only students with the best school leaving grades, which is usually an indication that they will be capable of success at university. Despite the competitive selection of engineering students into higher education, student retention and failure to graduate is a concern and student success is not guaranteed.

As the number and diversity of students in higher education increases it becomes more important to have an understanding of who our students are and what their academic journeys have entailed thus far. Despite aims to redress effects of South Africa's historical unjust policies, South Africa's education system remains unequal resulting in uneven education. We argue that a tailored educational provision that best suits the students currently in our mathematics classes will provide a strong foundation and a good chance for success. We acknowledge that there are various factors that influence success in higher education such as an alignment between students' expectations and their experiences, acclimatization to the new environment, a good work ethic, persistence and hard work, good time management, and a passion for the chosen field of study [2]. This research looks at the academic profile of a cohort of engineering students at a South African university. Knowledge of students' academic profiles help inform interventions that lead to addressing the diversity in our classes. Interventions based on students' academic proficiencies are imperative to provide the support students need to further their studies successfully [3].

The study of mathematics has an important bearing on the success of engineering students. Many research studies raise concerns about the transition from high school to university and students' preparedness to study higher education mathematics. Even for those students who meet the mathematics requirements for engineering enrolment, mathematics problems still persist and the lack of mathematical preparedness and mathematical proficiency remain a barrier to the study of engineering [4] and subsequently a barrier to retention of engineering students. The higher education landscape has changed considerably over the last 20 years and change has brought large numbers of students and with it diversity in mathematical proficiency, making the teaching and learning of mathematics a difficult terrain to navigate for both students and lecturers alike. We agree that "students must undertake a personal journey from their level of knowledge and skills at the point of entry to the level required to succeed in their chosen courses. All students have their own learning needs that must be met if they are to complete this journey successfully" [5]. This research paper reflects on the changing profile of our students with a view to questioning how our curricula and teaching and learning should change to meet and address this diversity to ensure success for all.

2 BACKGROUND

This research is situated in the Academic Support Programme for Engineering (ASPECT) at the University of Cape Town. ASPECT is a structured extended degree programme that allows students to complete a four-year engineering degree in five years, by spreading the load for the first two years over three years. Approximately 130 students join the Calculus 1 course and most follow on to Calculus 2. Both courses are taught by one lecturer (author 3) with assistance from tutors. Author 2 teaches repeat versions of Calculus 1 and Calculus 2. Author 3 teaches Calculus 3 each semester, with similar tutor support. Calculus 3 has an average of 98 students per semester, comprising students who pass the Calculus 1 and 2 sequence, students who pass the repeat courses of Calculus 1 and 2, and students repeating Calculus 3. The language of instruction is English.

The pedagogy subscribed to is one of students learning by actively engaging with the concepts. Lectures are interactive and tutorials center upon cooperative learning groups and are rooted in social constructivist theories of learning. A supportive learning environment is created through employing lecturers and tutors with expertise in teaching, scaffolding learning, showing patience and concern for students, encouraging study groups to form, and facilitating learning by appropriate use of technology.

2.1 Mathematics Competence in the Engineering Curriculum

A strong foundation in school mathematics is necessary to succeed at mathematics in tertiary studies. Negotiating learning in the various engineering disciplines requires a strong mathematical proficiency [6]. Mathematics forms the foundation of engineering studies, providing the engineer with logical thinking and problem solving skills. Taking into account the fundamental role that mathematics plays in engineering, [7] assert that more than providing basic knowledge for engineering, mathematics should foster critical thinking, develop problem solving and the capacity to analyse and accurately communicate information mathematically. In addition, [8] identify “different uses of mathematics in engineering practice: the direct usefulness of mathematical techniques and ideas to practice” and the “indirect usefulness - the ways in which mathematics contributes to the development of engineering expertise and judgment”.

2.2 Achievement In STEM Courses In Higher Education: Supporting Diversity

While science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) undergraduate programmes have been widely acknowledged as challenging to students - evidenced by low student achievement - they are also characterised by a lack of diversity and by achievement gaps based on gender, socio-economic and racial groupings [9]. Programs that provide multifaceted, comprehensive support have been shown to reduce performance disparities [10]. In the South African context, extended degree programmes are designed to increase access and success in STEM programmes by previously (and currently) disadvantaged groups.

Pedagogical interventions such as active learning benefit all students and are especially beneficial for underrepresented groups [11]. Students in courses designed for active learning not only reduced the achievement gap, but reported an increased sense of community and self-efficacy [12]. Active learning is one way that the ASPECT courses support student success [13]. Arguably, another way of supporting the success of a diverse student cohort is by analysing the student academic profile. Curricula, teaching and learning interventions informed by these profiles can be designed to increase epistemological access and success in STEM programmes for all students.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Context

The research participants were a cohort of 181 engineering students on an extended degree program who completed the last of three compulsory 12-week semesters of Calculus (Calculus 1, Calculus 2 and Calculus 3) in 2019. A minimum grade of 50% allows enrolment in the subsequent calculus course, with failed courses repeated in the following semester. Multiple repetitions of the same course are allowed.

3.1.1 Participants Demographic Profile: Race, gender and home language

The research cohort was 86% South African. The three largest of the 19 home language groups represented were English (48%), IsiXhosa (11%) and IsiZulu (11%). There were 114 male students and 67 female students. The race differentiation was 90 Black, 29 Coloured, 23 White, 17 Indian, 2 Chinese and 20 unknown due to students choosing not to convey their race.

3.2 Research Design

A quantitative analysis was used to explore the mathematical proficiencies of engineering students at a residential South African university, focussing on the academic preparedness of students and to identify groups of students to target for follow up qualitative research. The school leaving National Senior Certificate (NSC) mathematics examination grades and diagnostic information from the National Benchmark Tests (NBT) were used to explore students' entry level mathematical proficiency. Engineering students' mathematics performance in the three Calculus courses were analysed.

3.2.1 The assessments used: NSC, NBT and Calculus assessments

The National Senior Certificate (NSC) and National Benchmark Tests (NBT) complement each other and are both offered in English and Afrikaans, two of the 11 official languages in South Africa. The NSC mathematics examination, commonly referred to as "matric," signifies the culmination of twelve years of formal schooling and is a summative assessment which identifies to what extent a Grade 12 student has met the Curriculum Statement expectations as expressed in the Subject Assessment Guidelines.

The main objective of the NBT tests was to assess the entry level academic skills of candidates in Academic Literacy (AL), Quantitative Literacy (QL) and Mathematics (MAT). The NBT MAT test determines to what extent a school-leaver, who is applying to university, is prepared for the core mathematics demands of higher education study. The results of the tests are divided into four proficiency levels : basic (0% – 33%), lower intermediate (34% – 48%), upper intermediate (49% – 61%) and proficient (62% – 100%). The multiple choice NBT MAT test, aims to assess candidates' ability with respect to a number of mathematical topics which include problem solving and modelling, requiring the use of algebraic processes, as well as understanding and using functions represented in different ways, basic trigonometry, including graphs of trigonometric functions, problems requiring solution of trigonometric equations and application of trigonometric concepts, spatial perception (angles, symmetries, measurements, etc.), including representation and interpretation of two and three dimensional objects; analytic geometry and Euclidean geometry, data handling and probability and competent use of logical skills. Assessments for the Calculus 1 and Calculus 2 are both formative (weekly tutorial tests and 2-3 class tests in each course) and summative (3 hour written examination comprising 10-13 questions) focussing on problem solving and mathematical process skills.

3.3 Research Questions

We investigate the following questions :

1. Based on pre-university assessments and final grades for three semester-courses in calculus, what mathematical proficiency profiles can be identified?
2. Are the profiles different for other demographic factors?

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section we present the analysis of NSC, NBT and Calculus 1, 2 and 3 data.

4.1 National Senior Certificate (NSC) Data

From the 181 Calculus 3 students, mathematics grade scores for the school-exit National Senior Certificate (NSC) were obtained for 158 students. The remaining students had only letter grades such as A, B ($n = 11$) or did not have a mark available ($n = 12$).

High school mathematics grades had similar distributions for all students regardless of whether they passed or failed Calculus 3. The average NSC grades were 81.2% for passing students (females 80.1%, males 81.8%) and 80.5% for failing students (females 79.3%, males 81.0%). Figure 1 shows that Calculus 1 grades of non repeating Calculus 1 students are typically lower than high school NSC mathematics grades. Furthermore, higher grades for NSC Mathematics do not predict higher grades in Calculus 1.

Figure 1: National Senior Certificate Mathematics and first-attempt Calculus 1 grades

It is not surprising that the NSC mathematics results is not a good discriminator for success in Calculus since students are selected and enter the program with high NSC mathematics results. This raises a need for additional information to complement the NSC mathematics results which can provide more discriminatory information to direct our teaching and learning interventions.

4.2 National Test (NBT) Data

The NBT MAT test is intended to provide a complementary picture of a school-leavers readiness for higher education mathematics demands. Of the 181 students who completed Calculus 3 in 2019, 161 had written the National Benchmark Tests (NBT) before applying for university admission. The NBT Mathematics data reveals that 56 students (16 female, 40 male) were considered proficient and 105 students (47 female, 58 male) were in the intermediate category. Proficient students are most likely to be successful in higher education mathematics courses whilst those in the intermediate category will require appropriate support in the form of augmented or extended programmes or skills provision if they are likely to succeed.

School leaving NSC MAT grades and the mean grades for three semesters of calculus based on the NBT MAT categories are shown in Table 1. The Calculus 1, 2 and 3 grades for all groups were very similar, with female proficient students achieving the highest average grades in Calculus 3. For students who repeated courses, grades for the final attempt were used in analysis, which is one reason the Calculus 3 grades are much lower than the Calculus 1 and 2 grades - failing students are yet to repeat Calculus 3. Missing values were due to exemptions or in the case of Calculus 3 grades, non-completion of the course.

Table 1: Average grades for National Benchmark Test Mathematics, National Senior Certificate Mathematics and three consecutive Calculus courses

	NBT MAT (%)	NSC Mat (%)	Calculus 1(%)	Calculus 2(%)	Calculus 3(%)
Proficient Females	77.4 <i>n</i> = 16 <i>sd</i> = 7.1	84.2 <i>n</i> = 16 <i>sd</i> = 5.0	66.5 <i>n</i> = 16 <i>sd</i> = 12.7	66.6 <i>n</i> = 16 <i>sd</i> = 10.0	57.3 <i>n</i> = 14 <i>sd</i> = 13.6
Proficient Males	77.2 <i>n</i> = 40 <i>sd</i> = 7.1	84.2 <i>n</i> = 39 <i>sd</i> = 6.4	67.2 <i>n</i> = 39 <i>sd</i> = 12.0	64.1 <i>n</i> = 40 <i>sd</i> = 11.8	51.6 <i>n</i> = 37 <i>sd</i> = 14.9
Intermediate Females	54.8 <i>n</i> = 47 <i>sd</i> = 8.1	78.0 <i>n</i> = 47 <i>sd</i> = 8.5	66.1 <i>n</i> = 47 <i>sd</i> = 11.0	65.4 <i>n</i> = 47 <i>sd</i> = 12.4	52.5 <i>n</i> = 44 <i>sd</i> = 17.7
Intermediate Males	57.9 <i>n</i> = 58 <i>sd</i> = 8.1	80.6 <i>n</i> = 58 <i>sd</i> = 6.0	66.8 <i>n</i> = 56 <i>sd</i> = 10.9	65.4 <i>n</i> = 55 <i>sd</i> = 11.1	52.2 <i>n</i> = 56 <i>sd</i> = 16.6

The lower performance of proficient male students in Calculus 2 and Calculus 3 despite achieving the highest average grade in Calculus 1 may suggest that factors other than school mathematics preparation impact their success in mathematics beyond the first semester, which further research can explore.

Figure 2 shows the race and gender profile of students with intermediate and proficient NBT MAT grades.

Figure 2: NBT Mathematics profiles separated by race and gender

Figure 3 shows the final grades for Calculus 3 separated by race and gender. There is evidence that the support provided in Calculus 1,2 and 3 evens out the differences in the pre-university assessments and is helping to narrow the achievement gap between race and gender groups.

Figure 3: Calculus 3 grades separated by race and gender

Eighty-four students tested in the Academic Literacy (AL) proficient category whilst 77 students were intermediate, suggesting that the latter would have required curriculum integrated AL support to sufficiently cope with academic study at university. Most students with home languages other than English were Black (89%) compared to only 7% of Coloured, and 4% of White students. Accordingly, fewer Black students were proficient in NBT AL (26%), whilst 69% of the coloured students, 81% of the Indian students and 96% White students were proficient in NBT AL. Of the remaining 74% of black students who tested intermediate in AL only 6% reported English as their home language. This is not surprising as making meaning from English text is more challenging if English is not your first language. Thirty six students were positioned as proficient in NBT MAT and NBT AL, of these 83% were English speaking. Of the 30 students who were proficient in all three domains of the NBT 83% were English speaking. How this translates into our university courses would have to be carefully monitored in order to provide necessary language support.

The QL test results indicate 70 students as proficient and 91 as intermediate, a concerning result considering the course content in this faculty is heavily dependent on mathematical and quantitative knowledge and skills, and for the most part the coursework in engineering involves calculations and an understanding and manipulation of numbers. Of the 56 students proficient in NBT MAT only 37 (66%) were proficient in QL.

Figure 3 shows the cohort performance on the NBT MAT subdomains (in order from left to right): Algebraic processing (AP), number sense (NS), functions and graphs (F&G), trigonometric functions and graphs (T), and geometric reasoning (GR).

Figure 3: 2019 Calculus 3 cohort performance on NBT MAT subdomains

It is important to note that 50% of the cohort scored less than proficient for the key areas of algebraic processing and geometric reasoning that are foundational to engineering mathematics. Developing mastery of these topics, which are traditionally problematic for first year students in South Africa, is emphasised throughout the teaching in Calculus 1. The performance of the male students ($n = 98$) was slightly higher for all subdomains than for the female students ($n = 63$). In addition, the male students had higher medians, maximum scores and minimum scores in all subdomains.

NBT MAT scores were not very discriminating but subdomain data provided important diagnostic information indicating mathematical concepts students find problematic. AL and QL results raise further issues important in engineering mathematics performance.

4.3 Calculus 1 and Calculus 2 Data

The average Calculus 1 grade for English home language, NBT MAT proficient males was 68.6% ($n = 23$), compared to 65.4% ($n = 17$) for NBT MAT proficient males whose home language was different from the language of instruction. For female NBT MAT proficient students, average Calculus 1 grades were 70.1% ($n = 4$) and 55.6% ($n = 12$) for students with and without English as home language, respectively. While the numbers are low, the data supports that studying in a language different from home language affects performance.

Figure 4 shows the Calculus 1 and Calculus 2 grade distributions for students who passed Calculus 3 first time ($n = 115$), and students who failed Calculus 3 ($n = 31$) in 2019. Results for students who passed after more than one attempt ($n = 23$) and students who did not complete Calculus 3 ($n = 12$) were omitted from analysis. Students who failed Calculus 3 had a wider range of marks for Calculus 1 compared to Calculus 2. The only mark range with more students who failed rather than passed Calculus 3 was 50-59% for Calculus 2, suggesting that the majority of students who pass Calculus 2 with a mark below 60% will need additional preparation or additional time to pass Calculus 3. All students with Calculus 2 marks of 80% or above passed Calculus 3.

Figure 4: Calculus 1 and Calculus 2 grades for students who passed or failed Calculus 3

Only students with 80% or more in Calculus 2 are certain of passing Calculus 3. One factor can be a lack of mastery of content. Other factors contributing to failure in subsequent courses could be explored in further research, such as adjusting to more challenging content taught at a faster pace, a greater academic load from other courses, personal issues. Students with below 60% for Calculus 1 or Calculus 2 may need a further intervention before taking their next calculus course.

5 SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

5.1 Summary

The main aim of the research was to use student performance on school leaving assessments and first year calculus assessments to highlight the need for and to suggest ways of supporting students. Good pedagogy requires us to know the academic profile of our students, including their strengths and weaknesses in mathematics so that we may respond appropriately with a curriculum in line with their mathematical proficiencies, whilst being mindful of students for whom current curricula or teaching strategies are least effective.

Based on pre-university assessments and final grades for three semester-courses in calculus, mathematical proficiency profiles were identified and some of the profiles were different for other demographic factors. While pre-university assessments profile students' mathematical proficiency to inform interventions for Calculus 1, the differences measured by these assessments before starting university do not seem to significantly correlate with results in first-year Calculus courses. The university experience may have a greater impact on student success, at least for students in the extended degree programme. It may be that the extended degree programme is developing students sufficiently, but further research is needed to investigate this. The results of this research suggest that any invention directed to our first year Calculus students should involve academic literacy and quantitative literacy skills development. We suggest that the problematic school mathematics concepts be addressed for those students concerned in a blended learning intervention that is taken alongside their Calculus 1 course to help students bridge the gaps and therefore not allow these shortcoming to hamper their success in engineering mathematics.

A passing grade for Calculus 1, 2 and 3 is 50%. Students are able to pass a course by achieving high marks in one section and low marks in another, potentially creating gaps for courses that build on the neglected topics. Students in transition from Calculus 2 to Calculus 3, especially those with results of 50-59%, may be helped by interventions that address the issue of uneven engagement with course content by requiring mastery of all topics.

The next stage of this research will initiate interventions informed by these profiles to improve mathematical proficiencies especially at the interface from Calculus 2 to Calculus 3 where a steeper transition is observed. It is important to note that student support is not just a sum of services, interventions and learning opportunities provided but an “ethos” that is created. The ethos recognises that students have individual learning needs, that support should take the form of a variety of efforts both face to face and virtual, that learning development should not be stigmatised, that tutors and lecturers have an important role to play in supporting learning, that institutional support systems should be involved and engaged, and that students need to be motivated and inspired [5]. Any interventions initiated to address the transition to Calculus 3 should carefully consider this ethos if it is to succeed.

6 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

We acknowledge that, in addition to mathematics performance data, future research should include other factors which indicate students potential to succeed. Reasons for the lower achievement of proficient male students beyond their first calculus course could direct the development of support, such as the adjusting course load, providing support in courses other than mathematics, or behavioural or socio-psychological support. Based on the NBT AL analyses above, further research should explore how academic literacy can be supported for engineering students with home languages different from the language of instruction.

Future research could also profile the diversity of students as defined by an inter-relation of the various factors - academic, demographic and other - which have a bearing on student success. Further exploration is needed on how these profiles can be leveraged to support student success through the design of suitable interventions. Such research would be valuable in the light of student retention and success in STEM courses.

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